

COMPOSER CREATIVITY IN THE 20S-40S OF THE 20TH CENTURY

Shokirkhonov Bakhtiyor Botirkhonovich

Teacher of Namangan state pedagogical institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7312300>

Annotation: This article provides complete information about compositional creativity, changes in compositional creativity during the 20th century, famous composers and their activities.

Keywords: music, composer, work, analysis, rule, tune, melody, opportunity, creativity, specialist.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bastakorlik ijodiyoti, XX asr mobaynida bastakorlik ijodiyotidagi o'zgarishlar, mashhur bastakorlar va ularning faoliyati haqida to'liq ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: musiqa, bastakor, asar, tahlil, qoida, kuy, ohang, imkoniyat, ijod, mutaxxasis.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена полная информация о композиционном творчестве, изменениях в композиционном творчестве на протяжении XX века, известных композиторах и их деятельности.

Ключевые слова: музыка, композитор, произведение, анализ, правило, напев, мелодия, возможность, творчество, специалист.

The field of composition, which is mainly classical and partially enriched with folk art, has been forming and developing during the historical period of about one and a half, thousand years. The dictionary meaning of the word "composer" is also important to understand his many qualities. According to the definition given by the famous statist scientist I. Rajabov, "composer" is a Persian word, the root of which is the meaning of "connecting the elements that make up the melody" ("basta" - garden langan, "kor" - in the sense of work, employee). The essence of composition in music creation is directly related to certain laws and regulations. This means that the composer creates rhythmic and melodic versions of centuries-old traditional tunes, as well as introducing new scenes and ready-made climaxes to the tunes.[1] The artists who were able to adapt new poems to songs were also awarded the title of composer. It turned out that the composers also composed on the basis of the widely used melody patterns in music practice, and by connecting the ulam (melodies) with examples of poetry, they also created songs.

In this, the artistic tradition - the organic connection between the old and the new creative phenomenon - is manifested in the form of ideological-artistic features adopted and developed by the artists of the next period. In this process,

the talent of composers serves to demonstrate artistic skills within these traditions, to naturally create new opportunities, to reveal new aspects of “familiar” forms. Already, in the process of historical development, the musical values that have been passed down from teacher to student for centuries through artistic inheritance have acquired different manifestations in certain historical conditions. Therefore, the artistic tradition does not exclude innovation, but serves as an important ground and foundation for innovation. In order to enrich the established tradition with newness, of course, a deep understanding of the artistic tradition and high skill are required from each artist. There are definitely differences between the compositional creativity of the past and the compositional creativity of the present time. Composers are deep connoisseurs of classical music and folk music, master musicians and singers.[2]

Due to the establishment of special music educational institutions in our republic during the 20th century, priority was given to the specialty of European composition rather than traditional composition in the educational system. On the other hand, in the direction of musical creativity formed in the West, composer meant a certain “music writer” specialty.[3] Composers are the initiators of the renewal of our musical heritage.

Our composers are currently creating unique works on the basis of existing status categories. In addition, a new methodological direction and creative schools were formed in the work of my teacher. At the same time, various tunes, songs and chants, which are the creative products of the composer, are enriching our musical treasury. Music and singing activities have been of special importance in compositional creativity since ancient times. Even today, our composers show the interdependence of performance and creativity in their work. In the 20s - 40s of the 20th century, compositional creativity took an important place in the development of modern musical art. That is, since this period, composers who were in tune with the people of all ages living in the capital and regions, reflected the thoughts, dreams and hopes of the working masses, important events, cultural and spiritual changes in the life of the republic. reflected in their works.[4]

They perform popular and lyrical songs to classic and contemporary poets' poems on various topics in a traditional monophonic musical style, and to stage works from the heritage of folk music.[5] The materials of his dissertation on “Nazira traditions in the professional music of uzbek” were used. they created unique and unique musical works by using them positively. KHamza

KHakimzada Niyazi, whose reputation left a deep mark on the pages of “20th century Uzbek music history”, was one of the first among the favorite composers of our nation, Hamza (1889-1929) sought newness in the creation formed in the spirit of the new age.[6] He studied the singing traditions of Uzbek and other nations. He relied on them and used them creatively. In 1918-1928, he composed the following songs in the form of marches and waltzes: “Workers wake up”, “We are workers”, “Hoy workers”, “During the awakening” by his colleague Hafiz Muhyiddin Koryakubov and other singers. became famous in his performance. The poet and composer Hamza, who lived the dream of a new life, attached importance to using more finger weight in composing songs.

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